

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG X-GRADE STUDENTS STUDYING IN THE SCHOOLS AFFILIATED TO CBSE AND UP BOARD

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Abstract

Stress, defined as emotional or physical tension, can arise from events or thoughts that provoke feelings of anxiety, frustration, or nervousness. During examination periods, academic stress is a common cause of frustration for students. The primary objective of this study was to compare the academic stress of class Xth grade students studying in the schools affiliated to CBSE and UP Board. The main hypothesis was that "There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class Xth students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE and UP boards." The descriptive survey method was employed to conduct the study, and the population consisted of 10th-grade students enrolled in CBSE and UP Board schools in Ghaziabad city. Simple random sampling (lottery method) was used to select schools from each board (a total of four schools). From each selected school, students were chosen using random cluster sampling, resulting in a sample of 160 students (80 from CBSE and 80 from UP Board schools). Data were collected using the Student Stress Scale (SSS) developed by Dr. Zaki Akhtar. The t-test of significance was applied to analyze the data. The findings revealed a significant difference in academic stress between CBSE and UP Board students, with CBSE students reporting higher stress levels. The male students from CBSE board schools showcased higher level of academic stress as compared to UP board male students. The female students from UP board schools showcased higher level of academic stress as compared to females of CBSE board. Additionally, a significant gender-based difference in academic stress was also identified among CBSE students while in case of UP board students no significant difference was found.

Keywords: *Academic stress, gender, CBSE Board and UP Board.*

INTRODUCTION:

Stress, particularly academic stress, is a major factor contributing to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression, especially among students. Stress arises when individuals are unable to manage internal and external pressures, and when chronic, it can lead to psychological disorders. Nandamuri and Gowthami (2011) reported that curriculum and instructional guidelines were the primary sources of stress, accounting for 86%, followed by placement, evaluation, and teamwork-related issues at 63%. According to Sthavarmath and Patil (2022), rural students exhibit higher levels of academic stress, while urban students tend to experience greater anxiety. Both stress and anxiety were found to negatively impact academic performance and contribute to behavioral issues in high school students from both rural and urban areas. Depression, a leading global mental health issue, is expected to become the top contributor to global disease burden by 2030.

In students, excessive academic stress can lead to depression, anxiety, and other psychological disorders, which in turn affect their academic performance and overall well-being. Specifically, anxiety is observed in 8% of adolescents worldwide, and stress has a significant negative impact on their social, emotional, and academic outcomes. Busari (2012) found that stress among secondary school students contributed to depression and is related to the effect on academic results. Introduction of prevention and instruction Competencies and other coping

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strategies should be taken seriously. Stress, particularly in academic contexts, weakens the immune system and contributes to mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, mood swings, and even cardiovascular problems. Rani (2018) found that female students experienced higher levels of test anxiety compared to male students, and students from low socio-economic backgrounds exhibited more test anxiety than those from high socio-economic backgrounds. Kaur (2014) found that academic stress negatively affects adolescent mental health, with girls experiencing poorer mental well-being than boys. The study highlighted that parental pressure on students contributes to this decline in mental health. For students facing their first 10th-grade board examination, the pressure to manage syllabus completion within a limited timeframe and to compete with peers exacerbates stress levels. In India, academic stress is intensified by board examinations at the secondary and senior secondary levels, further exacerbating mental health problems among students.

NEED OF THE STUDY : Nagle and Sharma (2019) observed a significant increase in academic stress over time, primarily due to rising parental expectations and an increasingly competitive academic environment. This growing stress has adverse effects not only on students but also on families, society, and the nation as a whole. Deb et al. (2014) conducted a study in Kolkata involving 400 male schoolchildren from five high schools and found that 35% of students experienced high academic stress, while 37% exhibited high levels of anxiety. B & Naushad (2019) indicated that a significant difference exists in the Academic stress of adolescents in relation to gender. Female adolescents have higher Academic stress than male adolescents. Adolescents studying in Government and Private schools differ in their level of Academic stress.

Thus present study highlights the academic stress of students focusing on the role of board examinations as a significant stressor in the Indian educational context. The present study aims to assess the academic stress levels of 10th-grade students from CBSE and UP boards. Furthermore, it seeks to raise awareness among parents, teachers, counsellors, and the broader educational system about the importance of addressing this issue, as no recent studies have specifically examined the stress levels of students in these two boards during the 10th-grade examination at present time.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: Objectives of the study were formulated as under:

1. To compare the academic stress of class X students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board.
2. To compare the academic stress of class X male students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board.
3. To compare the academic stress of class X female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board.
4. To compare the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE board.
5. To compare the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to UP board.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY: Following hypotheses were constructed to achieve the above objectives:

(Ho)₁: There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board.

(Ho)₂: There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X male Students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE and UP board.

(Ho)₃: here is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board.

(Ho)₄: There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE board.

(Ho)₅: There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to UP board.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: The present study was delimited to the following:

1. The study was delimited to secondary school students studying in 10th standard only.
2. The study was delimited to the students studying in CBSE & U.P. board, Prayagraj only.
3. The study was confined to the private co-educational schools only.
4. The study was delimited to secondary schools situated in Ghaziabad city only.
5. The study was delimited to 160 students only.
6. The study was delimited to only one variable namely 'Academic Stress'.
7. The present study was confined to 't' test of significance only.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Research Method- Descriptive Survey method was used to conduct the study.

Population- All the students of 10th standard studying in CBSE & UP board schools situated in Ghaziabad city have been defined as the population of this study.

Sample size and sampling technique of the study –

The sample of present study comprises 160 students studying at secondary level (class-X) of private co-educational schools affiliated to CBSE and UP board and situated in Ghaziabad city. The selection of schools was done by 'Simple random sampling' technique (Lottery method) by selecting two-two schools from each school board, on the other hand 80-80 students were selected from both types of schools by employing random cluster sampling technique. One section of each class Xth students from each school was selected for the purpose of study.

Sample structure-

Research Tool Used:

Student Stress Scale (SSS AZ) constructed by Dr. Zaki Akhtar (2011) was used to collect the data from the students.

Variables involved in the study:

Dependent variable of the study was Academic stress, and independent variables were gender and board of school.

Statistical Technique used:

Statistical technique 't' test of significance has been used to analyse the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA:**HYPOTHESIS -1.0**

Hypothesis 1.0 is read as :- "There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board."

This hypothesis has been tested by employed 't' test of significance. Major values of the 't' test was as below-

Table -1.0
Academic stress of students studying in CBSE & UP Board

School Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't'	Description
CBSE	80	193.66	22.22	4.62	Null hypothesis rejected at both the levels of significance
U.P	80	173.06	26.37		

Table value at 0.01 = 2.64

Table value at 0.05 = 1.99 df = 158

Calculated 't' value = 4.62 't' value significant

The obtained 't' value is greater than its table value at 0.01 level as well as 0.05 level of significance for df 158, hence the null hypothesis was rejected, and it has been concluded here that students from the two different school boards showed varying levels of stress, with CBSE Board students experiencing higher academic stress.

The first conclusion corroborates the result of previous study conducted by kumar (2022) reported that CBSE and UP Board students have difference in level of Examination Phobia, but contradicts its next finding stating that UP Board students have higher Examination Phobia than that of CBSE board students.

HYPOTHESIS -2

Hypothesis 2.0 is read as :- " There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class Xth male Students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE and UP board."

This hypothesis has been tested by employed 't' test of significance. Major values of the 't' test was as below-

TABLE -2
Academic stress of Male students studying in CBSE and UP Board

School Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't'	Description
CBSE (Male students)	38	207.56	10.72	4.09	Null hypothesis rejected at both the levels of significance
UP board (Male students)	39	174.76	23.66		

Table value at 0.01 = 2.64

Table value at 0.05 = 1.99 df = 78

Calculated 't' value = 4.09 't' value significant

The obtained 't' value 4.09 is statistically significant at both the levels of significance. Thus, the Null hypothesis gets rejected and it has been concluded here that male students studying in both the school boards differ in stress level, showing higher stress level by CBSE Board students.

The findings of previous study conducted by Kumar (2022) stating, 'male students of CBSE and UP Board school have difference in level of Examination Phobia. Male students of CBSE have higher Examination Phobia than male students of UP Board school, supports the present finding'.

As we see more competition of marks, rank and score among CBSE board students and the male students of CBSE board are focussed than U.P Board students. In the investigator's opinion that it may be the reason behind this difference in stress level of CBSE and UP BOARD Male students of 10th standard. Other reason of this can be the competitive conditions with larger syllabus and curricular activities of CBSE board..

HYPOTHESIS -3.0

Hypothesis 3.0 is read as :- "There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class Xth female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE & UP board."

This hypothesis has been tested by employed 't' test of significance. Major values of the 't' test was as below-

TABLE-3.0
Academic stress of Female students studying in CBSE and UP Board

School Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't'	Description
CBSE (Female students)	42	174.56	23.66	4.09	Null hypothesis rejected at both the levels of significance
U.P. Board (Female students)	41	207.76	14.41		

Table value at 0.01 = 2.66

Table value at 0.05 = 1.99 df = 78

Calculated 't' value = 4.09 't' value significant

Interpretation

The obtained 't' value 4.09 is statistically significant at both the levels of significance, thus the Null hypothesis gets rejected and it has been concluded here that female students studying in both the school boards differ in stress level, showing higher academic stress level by UP Board female students i.e.

The previous study conducted by kumar (2022) contradicts this finding.

HYPOTHESIS -4.0

Hypothesis 4.0 is read - "There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to CBSE board."

This hypothesis has been tested by employed 't' test of significance. Major values of the 't' test was as below-

TABLE -4.0
Academic stress of Male and Female students studying in CBSE Board

School board	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Description
CBSE (Male students)	38	178.96	22.07	3.15	Null hypothesis rejected at both the levels of significance
CBSE (Female students)	42	207.56	10.72		

Table value at 0.01 = 2.64

Table value at 0.05 = 1.99 df = 78

calculated t value = 3.15 **'t' value Significant**

It is clear from the above table that the 't' value 3.15 is statistically significant at both the levels of significance. Thus, the Null hypothesis gets rejected and it has been concluded here that the male and female students studying in CBSE Board differed in stress level with the females experiencing more academic stress.

The previous study conducted by Rani (2018) stated that female students experienced more anxiety as compared to male students supports the present finding. The result of the another study conducted by Reddy, Menon & Thattil (2018) favours this finding as it stated that the dimensions of academic stress differed significantly among males and females and fear of failure was the only significant dimension that varied with respect to gender. One more study conducted by Sharma (2014) also supports present findings.

HYPOTHESIS -5.0

Hypothesis 5.0 is read as :- "There is no significant difference between the academic stress of class X male and female students studying in schools affiliated to UP board."

This hypothesis has been tested by employed 't' test of significance. Major values of the 't' test was as below-

Table -5.0
Academic stress of Male and Female students studying in UP Board

School Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't'	Description
UP Board (Male Students)	39	171.3	29.13	0.62	Null hypothesis accepted at both the levels of significance
UP Board (Female Students)	41	174.7	23.66		

Table value at 0.01 = 2.64

Table value at 0.05 = 1.99 df = 78

Calculated 't' value = 0.62 't' value **Not significant**

The obtained 't' value 0.62 is statistically non-significant at both levels of significance, thus, the Null hypothesis gets accepted, and it has been concluded here that male and female students studying in UP Board have no difference in their stress level.

The previous study conducted by Jamuna (2017) found no significant difference in academic stress between male and female students confirms the findings of present study. The other study conducted by Waghmare (2021) contradicts the present finding as it indicated a significant difference in stress among male and female students, but this also confirmed the higher mean of anxiety, depression and stress in females as compared to males as we can see in present analysis.

FINDINGS:

1. The students of CBSE board schools showcased higher level of academic stress as compared to UP board school students.
2. The male students from CBSE board schools showcased higher level of academic stress as compared to UP board male students.
3. The female students from UP board schools showcased higher level of academic stress as compared to females of CBSE board.
4. A significant gender difference in academic stress was observed among CBSE students, with female students reporting higher levels of stress than their male counterparts.
5. No significant gender difference was found in the academic stress of male and female students in the UP board. While females showed a slightly higher mean but this slight difference was not statistically significant.

CONCLUSION AND EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS :

The findings of this study underscore the need for a comprehensive approach to managing academic stress during board exams, particularly focusing on gender differences, board types, and student well-being. Key recommendations include training teachers, administrators, and counsellors to identify and address stress, especially among 10th-grade students. The examination system should be reformed to prioritize "assessment for learning" over high-stakes testing to reduce pressure. Schools should appoint counsellors to provide individualized support and integrate co-curricular activities like yoga and sports to alleviate stress. Special attention should be given to CBSE students, who experience higher levels of stress as compared to UP Board students, with targeted interventions to reduce academic pressure. Parents should create a supportive home environment that balances academics with emotional well-being. Additionally, teachers and parents should ensure a calm and stress-free

atmosphere for both male and female students, addressing the gender-specific differences in stress levels. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of addressing academic stress holistically at the individual, school, and family levels to improve mental health and academic outcomes. To mitigate these challenges, counsellors and health professionals must take proactive steps to raise awareness among parents and teachers about their critical role in fostering a supportive and healthy environment.

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